

Melting Behaviour of Fatty Alcohols and Their Binary Blends

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The m.p. of pure fatty alcohols from undecyl to nonadecyl are determined along with those of their corresponding pure fatty acids and their methyl esters; alternation in m.ps. does not occur in fatty alcohol series unlike the other two. Eutectic formation does not take place in the binary blends of fatty alcohols, but a maximum depression of the m.p. of the lower homologue occurs in presence of 11.0 ± 1.0 mole percent of higher one in the blend.

CONSIDERABLE work has been done on the melting behaviour of fatty acids and their blends^{1,4} but not so on fatty alcohols. Earlier work on fatty alcohols^{5,8} indicates alternation of m.p. upto dodecyl alcohol in the series, while the data given recently⁸ show the absence upto eicosanyl alcohol. Absence of eutectic formation of binary blends of even-chain fatty alcohols was reported⁹⁻¹⁰ and a maximum depression of m.p. below that of the lower homologues at 7 to 10 per cent of the higher one in blend was found to occur. Al-Mamun¹¹ confirmed this observation in case of few blends having odd chain fatty alcohols. The present report is a study of the melting behaviour of all the alcohols.

Experimental

Preparation of pure compounds: Glc-pure fatty acids from undecanoic to nonadecanoic acid and their methyl esters were prepared according to the procedures described earlier from this laboratory¹². All the even-chain fatty alcohols except tetradecyl were prepared by repeated vacuum fractional distillation. Tetradecyl and undecyl alcohols were prepared from respective glc-pure fatty acid-methyl ester by sodium reduction technique¹³ using xylene as inert solvent and tert-butanol as reducing solvent. The reaction product after hydrolysis with dilute H_2SO_4 was freed from fatty acids by washing the hexane solutions with dilute alkali till it showed the absence of fatty acid as adjudged by tlc. The alcohols were finally purified by vacuum fractional distillation.

The four odd chain alcohols, tridecyl-, penta-decyl-, hepta- and nona-decyl alcohols were synthesised by Grignard's route¹⁴, from their respective glc-pure even-chain alcohols. The even-chain alcohols were converted to alkyl iodides from which alkyl magnesium iodides were prepared; the intermediates were then condensed with para-formaldehyde followed by hydrolysis. The product

having small amounts of unconverted alkyl halides and/or alkanes were purified by the following procedure. The crude alcohols were sulfated in chloroform with chlorosulfonic acid, and the product was neutralised with butanolic NaOH. Part of the butanol was distilled off to remove the small amount of water azeotropically; sodium sulphate was removed by filtering the hot butanolic solution, and subsequent cooling precipitated the sodium salts of alkyl sulphates. The crystals were recrystallised from cold butanolic solution and desulphated by boiling with 1 N H_2SO_4 . The alcohol so liberated was finally purified by vacuum distillation to get tlc- and glc-pure odd-chain alcohols.

Determination of m.p.: Deaerated molten samples, to a height of 8-10 mm, were taken in open capillaries (1 mm i.d.) by dipping one end, and the other end was sealed carefully; while the samples were still in fluid state, the tubes were rotated in centrifuge so that the liquid moved towards the sealed end. All the samples were uniformly pretreated. They were chilled and kept in refrigerator overnight; subsequently the partly filled capillaries were dipped in water and warmed gradually to a temperature which was 2° below the respective predetermined approximate m.p.; the samples were maintained at that temperature for 2 h, chilled and stored at 0-5° for a week. The m.ps. were determined, in triplicate, by keeping the capillaries in an electrically heated and thermostatically controlled water bath, and gradually raising the temperature of the bath in stages.

Results and Discussion

The m.p. of fatty alcohols are between those of their corresponding fatty acids and methyl esters (Table 1), and the values are close to those reported in recent reviews³⁻⁵ (Fig. 1). This gradation of m.p. is, no doubt, due to the difference in the ability of molecules to associate through polar bonding,

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TABLE 1—MELTING POINTS OF FATTY ALCOHOLS, FATTY ACIDS AND METHYL ESTERS

No. of C-atoms in molecule*	M.p. (°C)		
	Fatty alcohols	Fatty acids	Methyl esters
11	15.3	28.5	—
12	23.5	44.5	5.3
13	29.9	41.8	5.1
14	37.0	53.9	18.7
15	44.5	52.1	18.3
16	49.4	63.0	29.9
17	54.0	61.0	29.1
18	57.6	69.6	39.0
19	61.5	68.3	39.2

* Refer to number of C-atoms of parent fatty acid.

Fig. 1. Relationship of m. p. and number of carbon atoms in the compound (No. of C-atoms of parent fatty acids plotted for the methyl esters): (O) present value and (x) reported value.

and the effect of such polar association between acids and alcohols is minimised as the non-polar chain length increases as seen by the non-parallel nature of the curves. The m.p. of all the alcohols fall on a smooth curve (Fig. 1), unlike for compounds of fatty acid and methyl ester series for which the m.p. curve of even-chain compounds is separate and is above that of the odd-chain compounds of the respective series. If odd- and even-chain compounds of the fatty acids and methyl esters are considered as separate homologous series, the points fall on smooth curves which are convex towards X-axis showing that m.p. increases with the increase in molecular weight for compounds of a type, but the differences between the adjacent homologues decrease as the respective series is ascended. It was shown¹⁵ that due to differences in tilting of the zig-zag chains of fatty acids, significant geometric differences between the crystal structure of even- and odd-chain acids occur causing alternation of m.p.

Similar thing may be happening for methyl esters causing alternation. In the case of fatty alcohols above undecanol, the crystalline structure may be such that only stable unchangeable forms are formed for both the odd and even alcohols in solid state causing the absence of alternation in the series. The differences in crystal forming habits of fatty acids and alcohols are further reflected in the melting behaviour of blends.

The phase diagrams of melting behaviour of the binary fatty alcohol blends (Figs. 2 and 3) clearly shows the absence of formation of (low melting) eutectics in the case of all the 26 fatty alcohol blends, unlike for fatty acid blends which form distinct eutectic blends^{11,4}. In the case of fatty alcohol blends, continuous solid solution formation appears to occur by the progressive addition of a higher homologue to a lower one, and a depression in the m.p. of the latter occurs to a maximum extent when 11 ± 1 mole per cent of the former is present (Figs. 2 and 3). The data relating to the maximum depression in m.p. is given in Table 2. The average depression of m.p. of a lower homologue that occurs depends on the difference in molecular weight of the individual alcohols in blends. When

Fig. 2. Melting behaviour of odd-odd and even-even fatty alcohol blends.

Fig. 3. Melting behaviour of odd-even fatty alcohol blends.

the molecular weight difference is 14, 28, 42, 56, 70 and 84 (component alcohols differing by 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 CH_2 groups, respectively), the average maximum-depression values are 0.42, 0.48, 0.60, 0.80, 0.95 and 1.1°, respectively; the concentration at which the depression occurs, however, remains in a narrow range of 11 ± 1 mole per cent of the higher, in all cases.

Perhaps due to formation of molecular complexes, between 30 and 70 mole per cent of the higher component, concaving curves in the phase diagrams appear for blends having components which differ in molecular weight by more than 42 units (Figs. 2 and 3).

The similarity in melting behaviour of odd-odd, odd-even and even-even blends can be attributed to the structural similarities of odd- and even-chain alcohols in solid crystalline state, unlike for fatty acids.

TABLE 2—MAXIMUM DEPRESSION OF M.P. OF LOWER COMPONENT AND MOLE PER CENT OF HIGHER ALCOHOL IN BLEND AT WHICH DEPRESSION OCCURS

Component of blends*	Difference in chain length of blends by	M %	Δ M.p. °C	Average Δ m.p.
13-14	1- CH_2	11.23	0.4	0.42
14-15		11.15	0.4	
15-16		10.55	0.4	
16-17		11.29	0.4	
17-18		11.09	0.5	
18-19	10.91	0.4		
13-15	2- CH_2	10.81	0.5	0.48
14-16		10.81	0.5	
15-17		10.85	0.5	
16-18		11.14	0.4	
17-19		10.83	0.5	
13-16	3- CH_2	10.69	0.7	0.6
14-17		10.88	0.5	
15-18		10.89	0.6	
16-19		10.62	0.6	
13-17	4- CH_2	10.93	0.9	0.7
14-18		11.89	0.8	
15-19		10.02	0.7	
13-18	5- CH_2	11.95	1.0	0.95
14-19		11.89	0.9	
13-19	6- CH_2	11.38	1.1	1.1

* Figures indicate number of C-atoms of constituent alcohols in binary blends.

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